

10 guidelines for an awesome poster

A “Streams of Thought” contribution by Andrea Popp.

A scientific poster is a communication tool explaining your work and encouraging conversation with colleagues. However, making a good poster is not easy. The following list provides ten guidelines for an awesome poster to help you to communicate your work more efficiently. You also find insider tips from recent EGU and AGU Outstanding Student Poster Award winners ([Skuyler Herzog](#), [Ingo Heidebüchel](#), and [Michael Stölzle](#)) and some great advice from the EGU Hydrology OSPP coordinators [Luisa Hopp](#) and [Julian Klaus](#).

1) Layout must be organized and easy to read

- do not overload your poster with information
- think big – choose a large font size and make graphs large enough to read
- use no more than 3 different fonts (generally sans serif fonts)
- use italics instead of underlining
- use colours to highlight, but not too many (2-3)
- choose a light and homogeneous background
- the progression of your poster should be obvious

2) Use brief and simple language

- use bullet points, no text blocks
- graphs say more than words, avoid text when possible
- be concise

Insight from OSP winner Ingo Heidebüchel:

“No text blocks! Some people say that a poster should explain itself if you are not there to walk people through. However, if you are there to explain the content of the poster, people will not read the text blocks but listen to your story. That means text blocks are mostly obsolete for the poster competition. Short bullet points are enough. Use the space for nice clean figures and structure the progression of your research clearly.”

Insight from OSP winner Michael Stölzle:

“The most important aspects of an awesome poster are good visualizations (4-7), enough space and empty space around the story.”

3) Present your (one!) message in a clear and logical way

- focus on a central message
- tell a story
- make your hypothesis clear
- let the story flow from left to right and from top to bottom

4) Have a unique feature to attract the audience

- think of an eye catcher
- be creative

- bring a laptop/tablet if you would like to show animations

Insight from OSP winner Michael Stölzle:

“Think about a strategy that makes people stop at your poster!”

Insight from OSP winner Ingo Heidbüchel:

“When I won, I actually had a laptop with me where I showed a small animated clip of my modeling results. Physical objects (like measuring devices or aquifer/landscape models) are also cool.”

Poster from Ingo Heidbüchel winning the OSP award at the EGU General Assembly in 2012.

5) Choose a catchy but informative title

- keep it brief – no more than two lines
- title should highlight core content
- use keywords
- do not use parentheses and acronyms!

6) Start preparing early

- think of your target audience
- practice presenting your poster – prepare an elevator pitch and a five minutes speech
- give a test run for colleagues to get feedback
- use appropriate software (e.g., Adobe Illustrator, PPT, LaTeX)

Insight from OSP winner Skuyler Herzog:

“I think of the overall poster presentation primarily as a normal conversation, with the poster as a prop or reference rather than the focal point. Failure to develop the conversation (think elevator pitch) can turn the poster into a crutch instead of an asset.”

7) Get rid of unnecessary details

- only include the things you need to explain
- delete anything that is not important

Insight from OSP winner Skuyler Herzog:

“I also reflect on the poster afterwards: were there any figures or results that I never pointed to? Cut them out. Did I repeatedly wish I had included a different diagram? Add it in. No presentation is perfect the first time, so be sure to reflect and iterate.”

Engineered Hyporheic Zones as Novel Water Quality Best Management Practice: Flow and Contaminant Attenuation in Constructed Stream Experiments

Abstract Number: H33C-1622

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Problem

- Nonpoint source pollution is a major threat to US water quality – it is difficult to identify and treat.
- The streambed **hyporheic zone (HZ)** is the “river’s liver” – it is a natural biofilter that can treat **nonpoint source pollution**.
- No established Best Management Practice effectively utilizes HZ.

HZ cross-section with microbially-mediated pathways for select contaminant attenuation. Lawrence et al. (2013).

Solution: BEST Engineered HZ

- Streambed permeability modifications:
 1. drive efficient hyporheic exchange
 2. control hyporheic residence time distributions (RTD)
 3. (optional) improve contaminant attenuation with reactive geomedia
- These engineered modules are termed **Biohydrochemical Enhancement structures for Streamwater Treatment (BEST)**.

MODFLOW flow vectors (left) and MODPATH residence times (right) in BEST module. BEST can create 7 L/s hyporheic exchange (per m width) over 100m coarse sand stream reach. Herzog et al. (2015).

Objectives

1. Compare HZ flow and RTD in constructed streams with and without BEST to previous simulations and physical experiments.
2. Quantify attenuation of contaminants from stormwater/recycled water in BEST vs. control streams at module and reach scales.
3. Compare streambed microbial community in BEST vs. control HZ.

Study Area

Constructed Stream Facility at Mines Park, Colorado School of Mines

- Dual stream reaches 13.5m long, 0.3m wide, 0.3m sediment depth
- Consistent 1% bed slope and impermeable EDPM liner
- All-sand (control) and 12 module BEST (test) conditions
- BEST modules: 1m spacing, sand/woodchip mix
- Homogeneous streambed sediments
- Controlled 1 L/s flow of recycled water from SB-MBR
- Can function in single-pass or recirculation mode

Constructed stream facility at Colorado School of Mines (left). A photo taken during construction (right) reveals the all-sand control on the left and the BEST stream on the right. BEST modules feature black impermeable plastic walls and a mixture of sand/woodchips geomedia for an added source of organic carbon.

Approach

1. Conducted thermal (via temp. probes) and electrical conductivity/resistivity (via EC probes and ProSys IRIS) tracer tests to track hyporheic exchanges, flowpaths, and residence times in BEST and control constructed stream reaches (Obj. 1).
2. Collected water samples along hyporheic flowpaths and surface reaches to quantify attenuation of select nutrients, metals, FIB, and trace organics in BEST and control constructed streams over time (Obj. 2).
3. Collected HZ sediment samples for microbial community and functional gene analysis (Obj. 3).

Example of individual flow paths delineated in BEST module tank.

Results

Tank dye experiments and geomedia column experiments have successfully demonstrated BEST flow dynamics and contaminant attenuation, respectively. However, the transition to full scale produced several logistical issues that are still being addressed.

Heat Tracing

- Inadequate signal propagation and probe spatial resolution
- Diurnal cycles confounded signals from heat element

EC/ER

- Inadequate EC probe spatial resolution
- ER pseudosections overwhelmed by low R; inversions underway

Water and Sediment Samples

- Need better flow data to select sample points and quantify results

ER pseudosection of BEST stream during NaCl tracer addition at t = 0 min. (A) and t = 45 min. (B).

Future Work

- Method refinement in tank experiments (Winter 2015/2016)
- Constructed stream experiments (Spring-Summer 2016)

Seeking advice on:

- Tracer techniques (DTS, ER, etc.) applied to HZ
- Hyporheic pore water sampling strategies

Broader Impacts

Urban streams with BEST can convey and treat water

- Meet TMDLs for nonpoint source pollution: water is cleaner exiting cities than entering
- Improve urban habitat, greenspace, & recreation
- Complementary to other Low Impact Development practices

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Poster from Skuyler Herzog winning the OSPA award at the AGU Fall Meeting in 2015.

8) Check everything before printing

- proofread and check spelling
- print A3 test version

9) Presenting at the conference

- start with general remarks about your work, then gradually get more detailed once your audience demands it
- ask colleagues to show up at your poster – having some audience leads to more audience
- if new audience arrives while you are still explaining to others, try to finish your speech first
- try to open up the circle of people standing around your poster to include as many as possible

Insight from OSP winner Ingo Heidbüchel:

“[...] Smiling and eye contact is always recommendable and also leaving room for questions from the audience.”

10) Use your poster to help yourself

- appreciate constructive feedback
- make notes of challenging questions from your audience which usually show weak points of your presentation or research
- lively discussions can help you to get new ideas, build new collaboration and even solve problems (maybe saving you from weeks of unnecessary work)

Insight from OSP winner Skuyler Herzog:

“It’s important to frame your presentation around the audience and your own goals. You might highlight different results in a primarily academic vs. industry conference. [...] I gave my poster at a time when I was struggling to upscale lab techniques to a field site, so I included a prominent section on my poster specifically seeking help in this area. This was a bit unusual, but I got a lot of great advice for my research.”

Improved baseflow characterization in mountainous catchments

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Abstract: EGU2015-10281, HS2.3.1

Shortcomings of conventional method

Global change adversely affects contributions of groundwater aquifers and other delayed sources to streamflow (e.g. snowmelt, outflow from wetlands or lakes). Based on frequency filtering of hydrograph, conventional graphical baseflow separation methods separate quickflow and baseflow from streamflow (Bj-H- or WMO-method [1,2]). The method was developed in humid, lowland catchments where groundwater is the dominant control of baseflow and quickflow is assumed to disappear after 5 days. These assumptions are not appropriate for higher elevation catchments!

Dischmabach, area: 42.8 km², elevation: 1680-3050 m a.s.l. BFI: 0.79
 Nival, area: 100 km², elevation: 1000-2000 m a.s.l. BFI: 0.71

BFI estimates are inverse to mean catchment elevation below 1600 m asl.
 Application UK-WMO baseflow separation leads to an overestimation of the baseflow component in higher elevation catchments.

- Only two contributing sources are considered due to the fixed filter width of 5 days.
- Is it realistic to assume that all contributions younger than 5 days are 'quickflow'?

Methods

DATA & CLASSIFICATION

NIVAL (NIV)
 NIVO-PLUVIAL (TRA)
 PLUVIAL superior (PLS)
 PLUVIAL inferior (PLI)

NEW BASEFLOW SEPARATION

DELAY CLASSES (P, M, C, S) based on streamflow regimes (D, S, M, C, S) and filter width (n).
 Relationship between BFI values and filter widths n is piecewise linear and the two breakpoints indicate a characteristic change of slope between segmented linear regressions (3,4).
 Maximum filter width n_{max} is identified when BFI is almost equal to a low flow metric (mean annual minimum flow / mean flow for all catchments).

COUWEL'S PREDICTABILITY

Couwel [5] developed a simple measure based on information theory to assess the uncertainty of a periodically fluctuating variable (here: mean monthly streamflow).
 Inverse uncertainty can be seen as Predictability P (P=1) which is additive composed of Constancy C and Contingency M (Seasonality).

Streamflow	Season	A	B	C	M=0	P=1
high	0	0	0	0	C=1	P=1
mean	30	30	30	30	M=0	P=1
low	0	0	0	0	C=0	P=1
low	0	0	30	30	M=1	P=1
low	0	30	0	0	C=0	P=1

Delayed contributions to streamflow

- << Shape, slope, derivation and baseline level of CDCs are important descriptors of delayed sources.
- << Short delayed contributions (quickflow) diminish after 3 days (Breakpoint 1).
- << Intermediate delays vary strongly among different catchment groups (Breakpoint 2).
- << Strong relationship (R²=0.99) is found between low flow metric (MAMMCI) and BFI60 (maximum filter width of 60 days).
- << BFI60 characterizes sustainability of baseflow.
- <> Delay-patterns varied among catchment groups and elevation.
- >> Longer delays in lowland (PLI), shorter delays in mountain (PLS+TRA), more intermediate delays in alpine catchments (NIV).

Baseflow characterization with constancy and seasonality of streamflow regimes

- The U-shaped relationship between "Mean Elevation" and "Predictability P" suggests more short-delayed contributions and smaller water storages in catchments between 800-1500 m asl.
- Higher Constancy C indicates stronger groundwater-control and is correlated with contributions in the "baseline delay" (P) > PLS > TRA / NIV in Dmalm.
- Higher Contingency M - as a measure for seasonality - indicates stronger control of transient, seasonal contributions and is correlated with intermediate delay class (NIV > TRA/PLS/PLI in class D_{intermediate}).
- Only weak correlations between Predictability P and other catchment characteristics (e.g. area, mean slope, drainage density) were found.

Multiple delayed contributions to streamflow

glacier, permafrost, springs, wetlands, irrigated meadows, hill moors, snow, snowmelt, infiltration, return flow, dams, lakes, riparian zone, flood plains, food retention, shallow GW, waste water, deep GW

Conclusions

- Graphical baseflow separation with variable filter widths allows to consider and identify multiple delayed contributions to streamflow.
- An elevation-based classification scheme is feasible to distinguish streamflow contribution in different delay classes.
- Origin of delayed sources can be identified by Couwel's Predictability (e.g. stormflow, snowmelt or groundwater depletion), which also indicates lowest water storage capacity in montane catchments.
- Delays shorter than 60 days are associated with constancy (glacial regimes) and/or seasonality (river regimes), delays longer than 60 days characterize the sustainability of baseflow.

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Poster from Michael Stölzle winning the OSP award at the EGU General Assembly in 2015.

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